

Recursion vs. Iteration Code Comprehension

Start of Block: intro

intro This experiment is about code comprehension. It is often thought that recursive code is hard to understand, especially for beginners. Our goal is to understand the cognitive mechanisms of reading recursive codes compared to iterative codes.

The experiment contains 4 short programming tasks. Note that the goal is not to evaluate your skill but to compare the difficulty of the tasks. The experiment is intended for developers with at least basic programming knowledge in Python and Java.

Participation in the experiment is anonymous and we do not collect any identifying information. The results will be used for research purposes only. You may retire at any point (even though we'd be happy if you stay with us until the end).

The experiment is expected to take 5-10 minutes. Continuing to the questionnaire indicates agreement to participate in the research.

End of Block: intro

Start of Block: Instructions

Instructions In the next pages you will receive three short python functions. Your task is to understand their functionality. **We are interested in the time needed to understand each function so please do not submit the results if you were interrupted or stopped in the middle.**

End of Block: Instructions

Start of Block: intro to BST Q

intro In the following question the argument to the function is the root to a non empty binary **search** tree. Click on the arrow when you are ready to start.

End of Block: intro to BST Q

Start of Block: iterative find max in BST

```
iterBST def function(node):
    if node is None:
        return 0
    current = node
    while current.right is not None:
        current = current.right
    return current.data
```

What is the functionality of this code segment?

time Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: iterative find max in BST

Start of Block: rec max BST

```
rec max BST def function(node):
    if node is None:
        return 0
    if node.right is None:
        return node.data
    return function(node.right)
```

What is the functionality of this code segment?

time Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: rec max BST

Start of Block: intro to linked list Q

intro In the following questions the arguments to the function is a head of a linked list. Click on the arrow when you are ready to start.

End of Block: intro to linked list Q

Start of Block: iter search

```
iter search def func(head, value):  
    while head is not None:  
        if head.val == value:  
            return True  
        else:  
            head = head.next  
    return False
```

What is the functionality of this code segment?

time iter serch list Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: iter search

Start of Block: rec search linked lise

```
REC search def func(head, value):
    if head is None:
        return False
    else:
        if head.val == value:
            return True
        else:
            return func(head.next, value)
```

What is the functionality of this code segment?

time rec search link Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: rec search linked list

Start of Block: REC reverse list

```
rec reverse
def func(node):
    if (node == None):
        return node
    if (node.next == None):
        return node
    node1 = func(node.next)
    node.next.next = node
    node.next = None
    return node1
```

What is the functionality of this code segment?

Q94 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: REC reverse list

Start of Block: iter reverse list

```
iter reverse def func(head: Node):  
    if head is None:  
        return None  
    current = head  
    prev = None  
    while current.next is not None:  
        next = current.next  
        current.next = prev  
        prev = current  
        current = next  
    current.next = prev  
    return current
```

What is the functionality of this code segment?

Q93 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: iter reverse list

Start of Block: intro to merge

Q98 In the following question, heads of two **sorted** linked lists are given.
Click on the arrow when you are ready to start.

End of Block: intro to merge

Start of Block: rec merge sorted lists

```
rec def func(list1: Node, list2: Node):
  if list1 is None:
    return list2
  if list2 is None:
    return list1
  if list1.value < list2.value:
    new_list = Node(list1.value)
    new_list.next = func(list1.next, list2)
  else:
    new_list = Node(list2.value)
    new_list.next = func(list1, list2.next)
  return new_list
```

What is the functionality of this code segment?

Q96 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: rec merge sorted lists

Start of Block: iter merge sorted lists

```
iter merge def func(list1: Node, list2: Node):
  new_list = Node(-1)
  ptr1 = list1
  ptr2 = list2
  ptr_new = new_list
```

```
while ptr1 is not None and ptr2 is not None:
    if ptr1.value < ptr2.value:
        ptr_new.next = Node(ptr1.value)
        ptr1 = ptr1.next
    else:
        ptr_new.next = Node(ptr2.value)
        ptr2 = ptr2.next
    ptr_new = ptr_new.next
while ptr1 is not None:
    ptr_new.next = Node(ptr1.value)
    ptr1 = ptr1.next
    ptr_new = ptr_new.next
while ptr2 is not None:
    ptr_new.next = Node(ptr2.value)
    ptr2 = ptr2.next
    ptr_new = ptr_new.next
return new_list.next
```

What is the functionality of this code segment?

Q99 Timing
First Click (1)
Last Click (2)
Page Submit (3)
Click Count (4)

End of Block: iter merge sorted lists

Start of Block: Demographic

Q1 what is your gender?

- male (1)
 - female (2)
 - Non-binary / third gender (3)
 - Prefer not to say (4)
-

Q2 What is your programming education?

- High School (1)
 - Current BSc student (2)
 - BSc degree (3)
 - MSc student or degree (4)
 - PhD student or degree (5)
 - Self taught, vocational training, army (6)
-

Q3 How many years of real programming experience (including army if relevant) do you have?

Q4 What is your profession?

- Profesional developer (1)
- Academic career / student (2)
- Other (3)

